

Using a Digital Camera and Skyglow Models to Perform a Transect Light Pollution Survey at a Planned Dark Sky Park

Tamás Ladányi¹

DOI:

Abstract: A new international dark sky park is planned at the High-Bakony Landscape Protection Area in Hungary. The local light pollution is negligible; the primary threat to the planned region is the city of Veszprém's light dome, located 20 km away. We started an imaging transect light pollution survey between the park and the city. Here we present the methodology and the preliminary results. A significant complication of the measurement is the variation in natural sky brightness due to the changes in airglow from night to night and also on an hourly timescale. Based on our recent results (Kolláth et al. 2025: "Conversion between measurement units used for night sky quality assessment with multispectral (RGB) cameras". JQSRT, 347,109636. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jqsrt.2025.109636>), it is possible to estimate the level of the 558 nm oxygen and 589 nm sodium airglow. We demonstrate how to homogenise the data based on this method. The measurements and models are used together to provide an estimate of the city's sky glow height at arbitrary locations.

Keywords: dark sky park; digital camera; light pollution; airglow.

Corresponding Author: tom.ladanyi@gmail.com

¹ Doctoral School of Chemistry and Environmental Sciences, University of Pannonia, Veszprém, Hungary